

The characteristics of the tidal swamp variety Siyam Kuning (right, foreground) contrast sharply with the erect leaves and short stature of derivatives obtained through treatment with ethyleneimine.

month shorter in growth duration and about 35 cm shorter in plant height, but were unaltered in agronomic or grain characteristics. Those intermediate in plant height, in the background of photoperiod sensitivity, also maintained most of the parent's original characteristics. Tillering was improved while spikelet number per panicle was slightly reduced.

Initial evaluation in the tidal swamps indicated that the mutant derivatives were well adapted. However, when seeded at Bandjarmasin, S. Kalimantan, Indonesia, on 25 March, most of the photoperiod-sensitive mutants were about 1 month later than Siyam Kuning. This was unexpected and will be further investigated in 1981 using several dates of planting.

If ethyleneimine is specific in altering culm length, it should be emphasized as a future tool in the improvement of specifically adapted traditional varieties. ■

Effect of flag leaf on grain yield of transplanted rice

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The flag leaf plays an important role in the assimilation and translocation of assimilates in the rice plant, and thus ultimately influences grain yield. Rice varieties may differ in the degree of the flag-leaf influence on grain yield and the importance of the flag leaf at different stages of panicle development.

A study at Allahabad during the 1975 wet season studied the influence of the flag leaf on grain yield in five rice varieties. The flag leaf was removed at panicle emergence, 7 days after panicle emergence, and 14 days after panicle emergence. The grain yields from those treatments and a treatment with intact flag leaves were compared (see table).

The difference in grain yield among

the rice varieties was significant. In all varieties, however, plants with intact flag leaves gave the highest grain yield. Removal of the flag leaf at any stage after panicle emergence caused significant reduction in grain yield. Grain

yield reduction was maximum when the flag leaf was removed immediately after panicle emergence. There was a marked improvement in grain yield in all varieties as the process of flag leaf removal was delayed. ■

Effect of flag leaf removal on grain yield of 5 rice varieties. Allahabad, India.

Rice variety	Grain yield ^a (g/55 tillers)			Flag leaf not removed
	0 d	7 d	14 d	
Sona	99.35	112.78	120.78	141.51
RP79-14	110.14	120.23	122.62	129.31
RP79-5	92.44	93.20	108.89	128.01
Ratna	97.99	101.54	107.54	125.11
Jaya	111.76	126.20	130.12	135.75
Mean	102.33	110.83	117.98	131.93
S.Em.	Varieties = 0.31		Treatments = 0.088	
CD (P = 0.01)	" = 0.86		" = 0.28	

^a Flag leaves were removed 0, 7, and 14 days after panicle emergence.

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